

Advancing Human-AI Collaboration in Industry

Welcome to AI-PRISM Newsletter #4!

This edition brings exciting updates from the project regarding AI and human-centered robotics. We explore **the future of human-AI interaction in the industrial metaverse**, recap the recent **3rd Consortium Meeting in Cluj-Napoca**, and showcase new developments in AI integration in painting line processes.

We also introduce the **AI-PRISM Open-Alliance** with insights from Bogdan Mursa on building collaborations for AI-driven innovation. Highlights include Sharath Chandra Akkaladevi's talk on sustainable robotics at the BRIAS Forum, breakthroughs in **computer vision** presented at the Trento Symposium, and our team's participation in the **European Big Data Value Forum 2024**.

Dive in to discover the latest in AI-PRISM's journey towards transforming industry with AI. Enjoy your reading!

AI-PRISM Science

The Future of Human-AI Interaction in the Industrial Metaverse

MetaStates: An Approach for Representing Human Workers' Psychophysiological States in the Industrial Metaverse

#AIPRISMinScience

Aitor Toichoa Eyam
Human-AI Interaction Researcher at
Tampere University (FAST-Lab)

Check out Aitor Toichoa Eyam's, from Tampere University's FAST-Lab, latest research on "MetaStates: An Approach for Representing Human Workers' Psychophysiological States in the Industrial Metaverse."

This innovative concept enhances digital human representations in industrial simulations, pushing forward advancements in Industry 5.0.

[Read more](#)

AI-PRISM Journey

AI-PRISM Project Update: Third Consortium Meeting Held in Cluj-Napoca

AI-PRISM recently held its **third project meeting at NTT DATA Romania in Cluj-Napoca on September 24-25, 2024**. This two-day event gathered the consortium to assess project milestones, share insights, and plan the next phases in developing AI-powered, human-centered robotics for smart manufacturing.

[Find out more](#)

and planning for the upcoming months.

Tech Advancements

Exploring the Future of Painting Line Processes with AI Integration

Last July an interesting **workshop was held at the Andreu World Est building in Valencia**. The event brought together operators from the Painting Line, focusing on both the painting and sanding processes, to share their insights and experiences about their daily routines, decision-making processes, and the most challenging and enjoyable aspects of their roles.

[Read more](#)

What is the AI-PRISM Open-Alliance? Establishing collaboration for AI-Driven Innovation

The **AI-PRISM Open-Alliance**, part of the AI-PRISM project, drives collaboration and AI adoption across industries by bringing together experts, businesses, and innovators. Focused on advancing human-centered robotics and smart manufacturing, the Alliance creates a dynamic ecosystem for AI development in Europe. In a recent interview, Bogdan Mursa from DIH Transilvania shared insights into the Alliance's mission and objectives.

[Know more](#)

AI-PRISM Events

AI-PRISM representatives from Transilvania IT Cluster and NTT Data Spain at the European Big Data Value Forum 2024

Our colleagues, Ana Gonzalez Segura from NTT Data Spain, and Andrei Martiniuc and Bogdan Mursa from Transilvania IT Cluster, participated in the **European Big Data Value Forum 2024**. EBDVF held as part of TechDays Hungary, a major series of events that took place between September 30 and October 8. Their attendance offered a valuable opportunity to connect with top technology providers from across Europe specializing in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and to promote the activities of the AI-PRISM Alliance.

[Read more](#)

Invited Talk by Sharath Chandra Akkaladevi at BRIAS Forum

On April 26, 2024, the **BRIAS Forum on Human-Robot Collaboration in Brussels** hosted an insightful talk by Sharath Chandra Akkaladevi on "Sustainable Robotics in Production Environments: Navigating Challenges and Achieving Innovations." The event attracted a diverse audience, with around 50 registrations from industry, academia, and research communities, making it a remarkable gathering for exploring sustainable advancements in robotics.

Explore Advances in Computer Vision at the Trento Symposium 2024

AI-PRISM proudly supported the 2024 edition of the CVTS event. The conference featured research and discussions in the field of computer vision and technological advancements.

[Learn more](#)

[Learn more](#)

STAY TUNED TO THE AI-PRISM SMART JOURNEY

[AI-PRISM Horizon Europe](#)

This email was sent to {{contact.EMAIL}}

You've received it because you've subscribed to our newsletter.

This newsletter has been prepared by the [AI-PRISM project](#). It does not reflect the opinion of any single AI-PRISM partner. The [AI-PRISM project](#) and its consortium partners are not liable for any consequence stemming from the reuse of this publication.

[View in browser](#) | [Unsubscribe](#)

